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Title: Carbon modelling beyond scientific production: a critical analysis of standards and European policies

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Keywords: “carbon modelling”; “life cycle assessment”; “biogenic carbon”; “standards harmonization”; “policy making”; “legislative mapping”.

Abstract: Efforts to mitigate climate change in European policies increasingly emphasize accurate carbon accounting along supply chains. This interdisciplinary study conducts a comprehensive grey literature analysis of standards, scientific publications, legislation and technical reports, to establish a framework for comparing carbon modelling standards. A preselection and screening process was developed based on criteria such as adherence to the life cycle assessment (LCA) approach, explicit carbon modelling content, alignment with EU legislative trends, and the binding nature of standards among others. The tools used for comparison are a set of LCA structures and LCA elements. These arise from the same grey literature review focusing on providing applied, harmonized and transversal insights of the different standards selected for comparison. The level of comprehensiveness within the whole LCA based standards comparison, and the interlinkage of concepts across standards are the key identifiers of this work. The findings include commonalities such as carbon bio-based content or electricity modelling. Nevertheless, notable discrepancies were observed in product scope, cut-off criteria, direct land-use change or carbon offsetting among others. This work provides suggestions to tackle this divergence for each LCA structure and across them. The goal is to map standards based on definitions, methods and divergence quantification. In all, this work suggests harmonization based on a comprehensive methodology to backbone standards comparison thus reducing trade-offs while providing a potential tool for policy making and LCA practitioners.

Abbreviations list:

- CC: climate change impact category
- CEN: European Committee for Standardization
- CF: Characterization Factor
- CFF: Circular Footprint Formula
- CAGR: Compound Annual Growth Rate
- CRCF: Carbon Removals Certification Framework
- dLUC: direct Land Use Change
- EF: Environmental Footprint
- EoL: End of Life
- EPD: Environmental Product Declaration
- E&R: emissions and removals
- FAO: Food and Agriculture Organization
- ICs: Impact categories
- IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
- JRC: Joint Research Centre
- iLUC: indirect Land Use Change
- ISO: International Organization for Standardization
- LCA: Life Cycle Assessment
- LULUCF: Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry
- OECD: Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
- PEF: Product Environmental Footprint
- sLUC: statistical Land Use Change

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate carbon modelling is a forefront tool for climate change mitigation, driven by both environmental urgency and significant market opportunities, with the carbon accounting software market projected to grow at a CAGR of 23.6% (2024-2032) (Fortune Business Insights, 2024). Moreover, aligning carbon accounting and reporting standards is the priority suggested to governments by the World Economic Forum (OCDE, 2023). At global level some efforts to harmonize the modelling include the Global Guidance on Environmental Life Cycle Impact Assessment Indicators of the United Nations Environmental Program (UNEP-GLAM). This initiative aims at enhancing global consensus on environmental life cycle impact assessment indicators, generating tangible and practical recommendations for different environmental indicators and characterization factors used in LCIA (European Platform on LCA, 2024). Moreover, one outcome of the 29th Conference of the Parties (COP29) is the approval of Article 6.4 mechanism of the Paris Agreement, which lays the foundation for countries to trade carbon emission reductions. Although this applies only to countries, companies are also indirectly affected (Reuters, 2024).

In this respect, the Resolution of the EU Parliament on Sustainable Carbon Cycles states that “enhanced carbon removal within products must build on robust carbon accounting methodologies that fully consider the upfront uptake of biogenic carbon into biomass (...) and taking into account indirect and supply chain emissions related to sequestration, biomass production” (European Parliament, 2023). Here, the incipient Joint Research Centre (JRC) technical report on carbon modelling update is part of the Environmental Footprint (EF) 4.0 update proposal. Despite the final version not being publicly available yet, there are official documents that provide several guidance on the topic (European Commission, 2024).

The life cycle assessment approach is a standardized tool that performs a “compilation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs and the potential environmental impacts of a product system throughout its life cycle” (ISO, 2006).

For this reason, this work uses the LCA framework to analyze and spot some differences among standards. Although ISO 14044 provides general rules on how to assess environmental impacts through the entire life cycle of processes and products, not all the carbon modelling standards follow an LCA approach, nor does ISO 14044 provide sufficient and univocal carbon modelling guidelines.

The existing scientific literature on biogenic carbon and LCA is limited in scope and lacks a comprehensive, harmonized approach. Some studies, like (Theresa Pscherer, 2024), focus narrowly on biogenic versus fossil carbon without addressing broader LCA aspects such as dLUC, cut-off criteria, energy modeling, or EoL. Others, like (Jinying Xu, 2024) provide descriptive, sector-specific insights but lack clear LCA modeling steps. Even detailed research (e.g., (Endrit Hoxha, 2020)) may miss key elements like data quality or iLUC. While some studies pursue other aims, such as organizational carbon footprinting, there is no existing research that thoroughly compares standards from a holistic life cycle perspective.

In summary, the main objective of this research is to enrich the discussion about the lack of harmonization in carbon accounting and modelling considering the LCA framework. This is

done by creating a novel LCA framework to analyze specific areas in carbon modelling and providing suggestions within inconsistencies to contribute to a more robust and harmonized methodology.

2. METHODS

We propose a harmonized methodology to analyze different standards of carbon modelling. The objective is to recognize the key standards on this topic, analyze them, and identify main gaps and inconsistencies in their application, considering scientific trends and the findings from legislative mapping. The main steps of this methodology are described below and summarized in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Summary of the methodology followed for literature and standards screening and comparison.

2.1. Scientific literature review and legislative mapping

Step 1. Review of literature from different sources (scientific papers, legislation, technical reports, etc.).

The following keywords or a combination among them were used to search in Google Scholar, Scopus and Web of Science: “standards”; “comparison”; “carbon modelling”; “carbon footprint”; “LCA”; “Life cycle assessment”.

The criterion for selecting scientific literature focuses on publications that consider an LCA approach for the comparison of standards explicitly mentioned for carbon modelling. Only publications from 2015 were considered given the fast-changing pace of carbon modelling. The screening of scientific literature only covers those standards which are addressed in European policies.

SCOPUS – **282**

TITLE-ABS-KEY (carbon" AND "standards" AND "comparison" OR "comparative" AND "Life Cycle Assessment" OR "LCA" ") AND PUBYEAR > 2014

Web of Science – **103** Smart Search (carbon "standards" "comparison" "comparative" assessment review comparative LCA)

Google Scholar: (standards Life cycle Assessment LCA carbon harmonization OR data). .Given the quantity of results, specific searches such as Journal of Cleaner Production or Journal of International Life Cycle Assessment were performed with the same keywords to funnel the search.

Figure 2. Selection of scientific literature focused on carbon modelling with an LCA approach.

While some scientific literature exists, it is often too narrow for comprehensive harmonization. (Theresa Pscherer, 2024) only focus on biogenic carbon and its comparison versus fossil carbon. Thus, a complete LCA analysis while avoiding trade-offs for standards is missing. For example: the linkage between biogenic carbon and dLUC, the variety of cut-off criteria, the energy modelling or the EoL rules among many others. In other studies, descriptive sector-specific analyses may not cover the precise steps to take for LCA modeling (Jinying Xu, 2024). For the construction sector (Haoran Lei, 2025) covers some critical LCA parameters such as biogenic

carbon or end of life for the construction sector, but they do not tackle direct land use change, which is highly relevant for the sourcing of certain construction materials (Mishra et al., 2022). It does neither cover other LCA structures such as the energy modelling or deepens on the particularities of quantitative modelling guidance (i.e.: cut-off criteria in ISO 14067:2018).

For the packaging sector (V. Tascione, 2024) provides a comparison of “methodological aspects”. Nevertheless, it is applied only a single sector and more called methodological aspects could be covered. For instance, energy modelling or data quality requirements. (Jia et al., 2022) focus on the economic analysis for the accounting rules for companies reports (i.e., order measurements), and not on products. (Lena Klaaßen, 2021) offer a framework to harmonize the scope 3 emissions by accounting for reporting inconsistency, boundary incompleteness, and activity exclusion, but they do not directly address the harmonization of standards based on the inconsistencies among them.

Other studies focus on biogenic carbon (Tellnes et al., 2017) or highlight the low recapture rate of stored CO₂ in forests with long rotation periods (Endrit Hoxha, 2020). However, even these studies can omit other critical LCA structures, such as data quality or indirect land use change (iLUC) analysis.

Regarding legislative mapping, the relationship between European Union (EU) legislation and standards is bidirectional, as standards can influence laws, and policies can in turn trigger harmonization rules. This study explored this dynamic in carbon modelling by examining standards mentioned within consulted legislation. The analyzed policies address the carbon footprint of products, elements of the biosphere like soil and vegetation, and forest management requirements.

Some of the main policies for carbon accounting include ETS, CBAM and Carbon removals EU certifications. Only the latter is analyzed in depth in this work. This is because ETS monitoring is not based on modelling, but on measuring emissions (European Commission, 2018) . Furthermore, this implementing regulation points to a set of standards for measuring emissions from equipment without addressing carbon modelling standards. CBAM, grounded on ETS (European Commission, 2025), neither refers to carbon modelling standards.

The criteria to analyze the EU certification framework for carbon removals is based on the degree of actuality, the clear reliance on modelling standards (i.e.: IPCC, EN 15804). Moreover, the technical reports, from this framework, such as CRETA, are structured based on the carbon footprint of products and elements of the biosphere, making its linkage easier with the LCA approach.

These technical reports assess methodologies for carbon removal quantification. However, these reports recommend different methodologies depending on the specific removal technology or practice. While there is consensus on standards for long-term biogenic carbon storage in buildings (EN 15804 and EN 15789), recommendations for carbon farming and permanent removals are tailored on a case-by-case basis. This leads to a lack of harmonization in the use of standards within the carbon removal sector. The complete analysis and conclusions of these

standards linked to legislative mapping are summarized in Table S1-B and Table S1-C in the supporting information S1.

To select the standards a structured process is followed: pre-selection criteria establish foundational suitability through broad, often binary (pass/fail) assessments, while selection criteria determine optimal fit through detailed, context-specific evaluations.

2.2. Standards pre-selection

Step 2. Pre-selection of the standards is based on LCA aspects:

- The standard's core methodology must be based on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) principles. This ensures that environmental impacts are evaluated from raw material extraction to gate, or grave, rather than being confined to a single operational phase (i.e., manufacture).
- Acknowledges carbon emissions and removals, regardless of the selected approach for biogenic carbon (i.e.: 0/0 or -1/+1).
- Quantifies dLUC carbon flows and, where applicable, iLUC; and/or provides guidance or mentions other impact categories.

2.3. Standards selection

Step 3. Final selection according to policy consistency and multisectorial coverage as non-exclusive criteria:

- Alignment with most recent prevailing European policies. The standard can be aligned with some of the definitions, metrics, requirements, or reporting format of key EU policies. For example: addressing at least some biobased products/services or compatibility with the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR).
- Degree of reliance on other standards. The standard outlines clear novelties from other standards and does not heavily rely on a group of them to define modelling criteria.
- Multisectoral coverage and availability (prioritizing the latest version if possible). The standard scope can be applied to any sector or overarches several (i.e., from agricultural to chemical industry).

The complete list of screened standards is available in Table S1-A of supporting information S1. Scientific literature and EU legislation were reviewed pre-selecting 22 standards and then, the following ten standards were screened for an in-depth analysis according to a set of criteria previously described:

- EF Recommendation 2021/2279.
- EN 15804:2012+A2 2019. Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Core rules for the product category of construction products.
- EN 16760:2015. Bio-based products - Life Cycle Assessment.
- EN 16485:2014. Round and saw timber - EPD PCR for wood and wood-based products for use in construction.
- ISO 14067:2018. Carbon footprint of products.

- ISO 21930:2017. Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works. Core rules for EPD of construction products and services.
- PAS 2050, 2011. Specification for the assessment of the life cycle GHG emissions of goods and services.
- ISO 22526-2:2020. Carbon and environmental footprint of bio-based plastics.
- GHG Protocol Land Use Sector and Removals (draft).
- ISO 14068:2023. Climate change management- Transition to net zero - Part 1: Carbon neutrality.

2.4.LCA structure and LCA element selection

Step 4. Definition and analysis of LCA structures and elements.

The LCA structures are groups of LCA elements aligned with a shared logic to evaluate LCA concepts, within each standard, for deeper analysis. The legislative trends, together with a carbon modelling focus, were the main principles to generate the most suitable LCA structures from the proposed LCA elements. Besides, these LCA structures are framed within the ISO 14040 for a better understanding of the proposed methodology (see Figure 2). Figure 2 also includes a summary of the most relevant sectors (many of those, biobased) for which the definition of the LCA structures is especially useful to focus the analysis on carbon modelling (bio-based products, particularly for food and feed, bioplastics and construction).

On the other hand, the LCA element is a defined unit of information within a broader system in LCA modelling that provides robust takeaways based on readily available data for most of the standards. All while facilitating the identification of the most suitable and unequivocal LCA structures.

For instance, for the LCA structure called “carbon content” (number 7 in Figure 3), the LCA elements are defined to answer the following questions:

- When should the carbon content be provided? (cradle to gate, inherent property, etc.)
- Only biogenic carbon? Or is carbon content in general also considered?
- Which are the calculation tools provided or indicated?

Figure 3. LCA structures from ISO 14040 framework.

Given the large amount of information processed in this study, the methodology proposes a two-phase analysis: a “general” phase to extract information from the evaluated documents and a “summary” phase to synthesize and interpret it. Not all standards contain data on all LCA structures or elements.

For the “summary” analysis indicators are provided to point the existence of statements or conclusions relating to the different LCA elements, as well as the binding nature or degree of obligation to be applied to each of these elements. This is especially relevant when analyzing standards.. The indicators are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Indicators for the formulation and binding nature of information retrieved from reviewed documents.

Summarized information	Indicator
Formulation of the statement	Literally stated
	Interpreted from the original statement
	Not mentioned
Binding nature	Shall/must/have to
	Should/may

This comprehensive application of LCA structures and elements connect standards, science and policy by framing key aspects of carbon modelling. This framework allows better identification of trade-offs as well as inconsistent patterns across standards to propose more transversal harmonization strategies as well as acknowledging further research needed.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Summary analysis of standards

As explained in the methodology section, a two-phase analysis was carried out to explore the selected standards: a “general” phase to extract information from the evaluated documents and a “summary” phase to synthesize and interpret the extracted data assisted by a symbol code. Supporting information S2 consists of an Excel file including both general and summary comparative analysis of the ten standards, considering the defined LCA structures and elements. Within this section, only the main comparative conclusions obtained from the summary analysis are shown for subsequent discussion. The LCA structures are presented according to the LCA framework (Figure 2) to arrange comparative study.

Our analysis reveals a landscape of partial alignment and significant divergence in carbon modelling standards. Synergies exist, such as the mandatory use of primary data for controlled processes and the conceptual acceptance of cradle-to-grave boundaries.

The lack of harmonization between standards in carbon modelling stems from the sectorial approach, the need to address specific policy requests such as EN 15804 for construction or EF Recommendation as well as the different priorities or identified gaps to tackle specific LCA structures (i.e., carbon offsetting, carbon content specifications) and the timing of the publications.

An analysis of the LCA structures is provided with special focus on the hot spots identified in the literature review and legislative mapping: system boundaries, cut-off criteria, biogenic carbon, direct land use change, end-of-life and carbon offsetting. The discussion is addressed from an attributional LCA perspective since this focuses on product systems thus allowing both a cross-sectorial analysis while avoiding divergence in the modelling analysis and recommendations.

A. LCA structures within the goal and scope.

Table 2 summarizes the results for the following LCA structures: products included, lifecycle stages, and cut-off criteria. Key results coming from this comparison among standards for each structure are summarized below.

Table 2. Results for each standard and LCA structures included in the goal and scope stage.

LCA struc.	EF Recommendation 2021/2279	EN 15804 2012 + A2 2019	EN 16760:2015	EN 16485 :2014	ISO 14067:2018
Products included	Literal Shall All PEF compliant products	Literal Shall any construction product and construction service	Literal Shall Biobased products in general excluding food, feed and energy. This includes products that are partially biobased.	Literal Shall Wood and wood-based in construction products	Literal Shall Products in general
Life cycles stages considered	Literal Shall all life cycle stages to be considered; Literal Shall co-products, by-products and waste streams of at least the foreground system shall be clearly identified; Literal Shall for intermediate products: distribution; use and end of life	Literal Shall production stage always Literal Shall production stage, end of life and benefits and loads for non-requirements compliant products. I.e.: biogenic carbon; Literal Shall construction, use and end-of-life.	Literal Shall all stages Literal Shall the exclusion of any life cycle stage justified	Literal Shall production stage	Literal Shall System boundaries consistent with the goal of the CFP study based on a significance threshold (contribution) level. Literal Shall significance threshold (contribution) clearly justified.
Cut-off criteria	Literal Shall explicit justification of cut off criteria; $\approx 3\%$ cut off criteria based on material, energy flows, and the single score	Literal Shall explicit justification of cut off criteria; Literal Shall 1% cut off criteria based on total mass input on a process or renewable and non-renewable primary energy usage. Literal Shall total neglected input flows per modules $<5\%$ of energy usage and mass.	Literal Shall explicit criteria/justification; Literal Shall cut off criteria based on mass, energy or environmental significance. Interpreted Shall cut off criteria based on mass, energy or environmental significance. No quantification.	As in EN 15804 Literal Shall explicit justification of cut off criteria; Literal Shall 1% cut off criteria based on total mass input on a process or renewable and non-renewable primary energy usage. Literal Shall total neglected input flows per modules $<5\%$ of energy usage and mass.	Literal Shall explicit justification of cut off criteria; Literal Shall cut off criteria based on mass, energy or environmental significance. No quantification.
LCA struc.	ISO 21930:2017	PAS 2050, 2011	ISO 22526-2:2020	GHG Protocol Draft Land use sector and removals	ISO 14068:2023

Products included	Literal Shall Construction products	Literal Shall generically applicable to a wide range of goods and services	Literal Shall Biobased plastics	Literal Shall Products, activities and companies	Literal Shall applicable to a wide range of subjects: organizations, events, financial institutions and products.
Life cycles stages considered	Literal Shall production stage. Literal Shall Cradle to gate (modules A1-A3), Literal Shall cradle to gate with options (includes mandatory + optional information modules like EoL); cradle to grave.	Literal Shall all material life cycle stages. Literal Shall Cradle to gate including waste management arising from these processes and end of life scenarios for packaging information Literal Shall cradle to grave	Literal Shall Cradle to gate Literal Shall Partial CFPs can be added together to quantify the CFP.	Literal Shall scope definition based on organizational boundaries and consistent for all accounting categories. Literal Shall Cradle to gate: gate to gate; gate to grave or cradle to grave depending on the product	Literal Shall for business-to-consumer communication full life cycle; contextualization of the carbon footprint to be documented; uncertainties defining the boundary to be documented
Cut-off criteria	Literal Shall Explicit justification of cut off criteria; Literal Shall cut-off criteria shall be 1 % of primary resources, 1% total mass input of that unit process or environmental impacts.	Interpreted Shall Explicit justification of cut off criteria; Literal Shall > 1% of the anticipated total GHG emissions. Materiality threshold: 1%	Literal Shall Cover the whole product, not only its bio-based parts. Interpreted Shall cut off criteria in line with ISO 14067	Literal Shall only the cut-off date is explicitly mentioned	See ISO 14067

Products included. All the standards cover bio-based products or are related to the construction sector. While some standards, like ISO 21930 and PAS 2050-2011, explicitly consider services as well. A broader definition of "product" is adopted in a limited number of standards. Some standards extend the concept to encompass companies (GHG Protocol draft on Land Sector and Removals) or events (ISO 14068). It is important to note that food and feed are specifically excluded from the scope of EN 16760:2015.

Life cycle stages considered. Two main life cycle approaches were identified: cradle to grave and cradle to gate. The production stage is mandatory. This also applies for intermediate products in PEF. In some cases, EoL is mandatory regarding products (ISO 22526:2020) or the packaging of the products (PAS 2050:2011). ISO 22526:2020 allows the cradle to grave analysis by bringing partial CFPs together. The exclusion of any life cycle stage shall be justified in EN 16760 or consistent with significance threshold in ISO 14067:2018.

This diversity in life cycle stages modelling implies strong differences in the carbon (partial or total) footprint as well as the interpretation. Although the cradle to gate approach provides flexibility when the use of the product is not well known or different options are available, this can open the door to incorrect carbon accounting. For example, allocating carbon removals from carbon content to the product without assigning the emissions from landfill disposal as well, thus creating a burden for the final user that needs to be clarified (Liang et al., 2023).

This work encourages clear disclosure of life cycle stages considered and consistency with end-of-life modelling. As minimum requirements, pre-processing and manufacturing phases disclosure and clear explanation of the cut-off criteria should be covered. As long as possible, cradle to gate should be avoided and clear disclosure and justification of this approach is needed for comparative purposes. The addition of CFPs is not recommended following scientific evidence (Endrit Hoxha, 2020), but, if performed, should match functional unit, cut-off criteria and system boundaries avoiding any double counting or neglecting potential significant processes (i.e., packaging or transportation if relevant). Moreover, carbon content should be used only as additional information and focus on the system boundaries net emissions and removals.

The suggested approach is followed by many of the analyzed standards like ISO 14067, or EF so its applicability both for LCA practitioners (i.e., ILCD dataset format) and ESG reporting is immediate.

Cut-off criteria. Its justification is a nearly universal requirement across standards, though the criteria diverge significantly. Some mandate quantitative thresholds based on mass and energy (e.g., PEF, EN 15804), with some specifying limits per module. In contrast, others rely on qualitative 'environmental significance' without providing a uniform definition (e.g., ISO 14067, EN 16760). In the GHG Protocol Draft guidance on Land Sector and Removals only the cut-off date is explicitly mentioned.

This work advocates quantitative and traceable cut-off criteria. I.e., mass significance or quantitative % of total carbon footprint. Including clear cut-off criteria benefits LCA practitioners but demands additional effort for ESG reporting (i.e., based on GHG Protocol). Although this quantification can entail more workload in first instance since the carbon footprint of certain flows are not known (i.e., the relevance of a catalyst (Moreno et al., 2020)), this untaps the potential to identify new hot spots and ecodesign opportunities. To avoid excessive complexity general cut-off criteria based on mass or energy (i.e., 5%) could be used if the associated product or flow does not carry significant carbon footprint per functional unit (i.e., plastic film for packaging of certain large products).

Table 3. Results for each standard and LCA structures included in inventory analysis.

LCA struc.	EF Recommendation 2021/2279	EN 15804 2012 + A2 2019	EN 16760:2015	EN 16485 :2014	ISO 14067:2018
Data collection and quality requirements	Literal Shall Product modelling and company-specific data from the specific product covered in the study; Literal Shall EF compliant dataset reported and validated.	Literal Shall Datasets use ILCD format and nomenclature; Literal Shall EF compliant datasets assessed; Literal Shall Product manufacture requires company specific data; Literal Shall Data quality to be assessed in term of geography, time and technological representativeness.	Literal Shall EoL model clearly documented and reported in the study (e.g. as an appendix)	Literal Shall Datasets use ILCD format and nomenclature; Literal Shall EF compliant datasets assessed.	Literal Shall Site-specific data collected for individual processes under the organization's control. Literal Shall Also most important processes (at least 80 % to the CFP); Literal Shall Secondary data only where the collection of primary data is not practicable, or for processes of minor importance.
Energy modelling	Literal Shall electricity mix follows a hierarchical order. The supplier-specific electricity for the product is to be used if for the given country, there is a 100% tracking system in place. The last option is the EU residual mix. Literal Shall proving renewable sourcing of electricity and no double counting guarantee	Literal Shall specific data if the producer has influence on the given electricity process. Literal Shall Generic data for electricity generation. Literal Shall assumptions about electricity production	Not mentioned 0	Literal Shall in case of exporting heat or electricity in internal production, the impacts of fuels allocation is based on exergy. Also part of the product system to extend to which heat and electricity is used within the product system	Literal Shall electricity, heat and cooling and compressed air. Literal Shall Use life cycle data for internal electricity generation and consumption, with no contractual instrument for sale to a third party. Literal Shall Use life cycle specific data from a supplier when guarantee provided via contractual instrument.
All emissions and removals with emphasis on biogenic carbon	Literal Shall Biogenic emissions and removals accounted but 0/0 approach in characterization. Literal Shall Mass allocation for biogenic carbon flows	Literal Shall -1/+1 approach but for native forest-> LULUC.	Literal Shall -1/+1 and 0/0	Literal Shall -1/+1 or 0/0 approach depending on if the origin of the wood is from countries that have decided to account for Art. 3.4 of the Kyoto Protocol or for wood originating from forests which are operating under established certification schemes for sustainable forest management".	Literal Shall -1/+1 approach, includes all GHG emissions and removals from biogenic carbon
Carbon content	Literal Shall Biogenic carbon content for intermediate products shall always be provided as additional technical information. For finalized products is not explicitly mandatory, but has to allow climate change modelling	Literal Shall Carbon content of a product leaving the factory gate and: If mass of biogenic carbon >5%. Only biogenic carbon content to be reported. May be omitted; "Can	Literal Shall Biogenic carbon content is an inherent property. Literal Shall Only biogenic carbon content to be reported	Literal Shall energy and biogenic carbon content are accounted as inherent properties	Literal Shall provide biogenic carbon content but separately in the CFP report

		be measured or calculated according to EN 16449, Wood and wood-based products"			
Carbon storage	Literal Shall Developments will be considered in order to keep the method updated with scientific evidence and expert consensus	Literal Shall Temporary carbon storage, delayed emissions and biogenic carbon storage not to be included in the GWP calculation	Literal Shall Guidance for temporary carbon accounting	Literal Shall Storage time is the reference service life., Modelling requirements are the same as in EN 15805	Literal Shall supplementary calculation that acknowledges the impact of biogenic carbon storage due to timing is not to be part of CFP.
Direct land use change	Literal Shall All E&R included except removals from native forests. Soil carbon storage may be included as additional env. info. Carbon pools indirectly considered from IPCC Guidelines from PAS 2050 if Annex C emissions are not available.	Literal Shall All E&R included except for removals from native forests. Soil carbon storage may be included as additional environmental information. Shall follow latest available PEF guidance	Literal Shall CO2 and non-CO2 emissions and CO2 removals resulting from carbon stock change, related to LUC and improved agricultural management	Literal Shall double counting to be avoided. Emissions from deforestation to be separately reported.	Literal Shall dLUC to be reported. Site-specific data to be reported transparently. Methods to be chosen that are internationally recognised such as IPCC Guidelines. Time period selection to be documented and justified.
iLUC	Literal Shall May be included under additional information	Not mentioned	Literal Shall only in the interpretation phase	Not mentioned	Literal once an internationally agreed procedure exists
Land management practices - CC	Literal Should SOC only as additional information	Not mentioned	Literal Should only net human interventions in land management to be inventoried	As EN 15804	Literal Shall net increase in biomass carbon from land use practice to be included if measures to address permanence
EoL	Literal Shall modelled as CFF. Reuse/refurbishment modelled as lifetime extension. Energy recovery shall be modelled and no minimum requirements. Degradation includes both fossil and biogenic emissions.	Literal Should Modelling explained in ANNEX D. Recycled materials can be secondary materials. Literal Shall Degradation includes both fossil and biogenic emissions. Minimum requisite for energy recovery = 60 %.	Literal Should EoL carbon modelling for bio-based special care. See CEN/TR 16957. Literal Shall assumptions to be clearly reported and documented, also product characteristics.	Same as EN 15804	Literal Shall all emissions and removals in EoL to be included. Two possible allocation methods: open-loop and closed loop:
Loads, benefits & offsetting	Literal Shall Offsetting not to be included in PEF study, but as additional env. info.	Literal Shall Carbon offset not to be included in the GWP calculation.	Not mentioned	Same as EN 15804	Literal Shall No offsetting can be considered.
LCA struc.	ISO 21930:2017	PAS 2050, 2011	ISO 22526-2:2020	GHG Protocol Draft Land use sector and removals	ISO 14068:2023

<p>Data collection and quality requirements</p>	<p>Literal Shall Site-specific data collected for processes under organization’s influence. Literal Shall When there is more than one factory, generate a “representative average”; Literal Shall Secondary data for not under organization’s control.</p>	<p>Literal Shall Site-specific data collected for processes under organization’s control that cumulatively contribute 10% or more to the upstream GHG emissions.</p>	<p>Literal Shall Site-specific data collected for individual processes under the organization’s control. Literal Shall Also most important processes (at least 80 % to the CFP); Literal Shall Secondary data only where the collection of primary data is not practicable, or for processes of minor importance.</p>	<p>Literal Shall removals with product storage only if the removals are statistically significant and companies provide quantitative uncertainty estimates</p>	<p>Literal Shall carbon neutrality plan science-based approach, climate change mitigation potential from a technical, economic and social perspective and other requisites</p>
<p>Energy modelling</p>	<p>Literal Shall For information modules (use, etc.). Literal Shall Generic data may be use for modelling electricity generation. Literal Shall Electricity production assumptions</p>	<p>Literal Shall Emission factor consistent with PAS and no double counting demonstrated. Literal Shall Removals and emissions associated with electricity generation included. Literal Shall avoided emissions based on average GHG emissions of electricity grid. Literal Shall heat from CHP, less avoided burden, allocated between heat and electricity used.</p>	<p>Literal Shall GHG emissions and removals from electricity not separately documented in P-CFP following ISO 14067:2018</p>	<p>Literal Should supplier's electricity to be used if they can deliver a specific emission factor. Otherwise, regional average.</p>	<p>Literal Shall market based approach only if supplier able to guarantee the assured electricity product with a unique claim. Literal Shall renewable energy hierarchy and there is a separate certification process for bio-fuels and bio-based materials that can results in GHG emission reduction</p>
<p>All emissions and removals with emphasis on biogenic carbon</p>	<p>Literal Shall -1/+1 approach (CFs as EN 15804). Floor wood products -1/+1 approach is only allowed when the wood originates from sustainably managed forests (PEFC, FSC, CSA). Moreover exports/imports are characterized +1/-1. Interpreted Shall Biogenic carbon reflects physical flows</p>	<p>Literal Shall -1/+1 approach but some emissions and removals may be excluded if they fulfil the requisites.</p>	<p>Literal Shall -1/+1 approach as ISO 14067:2018</p>	<p>Literal Shall -1/+1 or 0/0</p>	<p>Literal Shall -1/+1 approach, includes all GHG emissions and removals from biogenic carbon (from ISO 14067)</p>
<p>Carbon content</p>	<p>Literal Shall biogenic carbon in the product that leaves the system is to be declared</p>	<p>Literal Shall carbon incorporated to plants with a life of at least 20 years, which are part of product system, to be treated as soil carbon.</p>	<p>Literal Shall Formulas for biobased synthetic polymer are provided</p>	<p>Literal Shall primary data to include carbon content; Literal Shall secondary data may be used to</p>	<p>Literal Shall for reporting biogenic carbon separately GHG Protocol Product life cycle accounting is considered consistent with ISO 14067</p>

				support carbon stock change calculations	
Carbon storage	Not mentioned	Literal Shall Carbon storage is considered for when exceeding 100 years and excepting carbon stock in managed forests. Literal Shall Data sources and the life cycle assessment behind carbon storage are to be recorded and retained.	Literal Shall Not included in the P-CFP. For reporting see ISO 14067:2018.	Literal Shall specific requisites for companies to declare carbon storage mainly related to land carbon stock changes.	Interpreted Shall To make GHG Protocol consistent with ISO 14067 carbon storage may be reported but as a separate subcategory and not included in the final GHG result.
dLUC	Literal Shall dLUC assessed by recognised methods like IPCC Literal Shall sustainably managed forests wood may be accounted as zero emissions for LUC	Literal Shall dLUC to be assessed based on Annex C & IPCC Guide.	Literal Shall dLUC E&R to be assessed	Literal Shall dLUC emissions and removals to be assessed	Interpreted Shall emissions and removals from dLUC to be reported separately
iLUC	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	Literal Shall be considered for inclusion in P-CFP	Literal Shall be considered for inclusion in P-CFP	Literal Shall iLUC, if reported, shall be done separately
Land management practices - CC	Interpreted Should Requisites are the same as stated for LUC only if there is a land management change. If there is none, no modelling requirements are provided	Literal Shall and management practices are excluded. Literal Should Only as supplementary requirements	Literal Should management of land emissions and removals to be included	Literal Shall when a minimal impact from land management; account changes in biomass.	See ISO 14067
EoL	Literal Shall energy recovery to be based on existing technology and current practice. Literal Should Loads and benefits from E recovery from landfill to be considered optionally.	Literal Shall EoL to be included. A distinction between recycled content with same and different inherent properties. Calculation explained for weighted delayed emissions	Not mentioned	Literal Shall product lifetime, waste treatment and time boundary for scope 3 to be provided. Literal Should all emissions from waste to be accounted. Allocation method guidance is provided. Any claims of avoided emissions not to be included or deducted from, the scope 3, but reported separately.	See ISO 14067
Loads, benefits & offsetting	Literal Shall to be reported separately. All net output flows reporting in module D Not mentioned Offsetting	Literal Shall No offsetting can be considered.	Not mentioned	Literal Shall offsetting part of GHG accounting but reported separately. Measured relative to	Literal Shall Before offsetting, shall reduce and implement GHG removals. Additional req. needed.

				counterfactual baseline.	
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Data collection and quality requirement. Depending on standards scope, reporting primary data varies from processes under an organization's control (i.e., PEF) to company's value chain partners operation (GHG Protocol). I.e., products for EF vs. products, organizations or events for GHG Protocol.

Several ISO standards and PAS 2050 extend this primary data requirement to upstream processes that contribute significantly to the total footprint, with thresholds ranging from 10% to 80% (most important emissions not under financial or operational control. I.e., ISO 14067).

Secondary data is typically permitted only when primary data collection is not feasible. Data quality requirements are more specific for ILCD (International Life Cycle Data System) reliant guidelines (EN 15804 or EF) than other standards that rely on representative data (i.e., ISO 14067) probably as the former are shaped by policy alignment towards a particular method (EF) rather than addressing the broader complexity of an ISO standard (European Commission, 2025) that requires broader acceptance.

Therefore, we encourage the use of primary data that is under manufacturer's control and, for consistency, using significance criteria aligned with the quantitative cut-off criteria. For secondary datasets ILCD compliant are considered a robust resource thanks to the tools provided for data analysis, validation and sharing through Life Cycle Data Network (LCDN) (UNEP, 2020).

Data quality and requirements are one of the cornerstones for carbon modelling transparency and traceability. From the analyzed standards we opt for the ILCD which is followed in PEF, EN 15804 and EN 16485. This is, for the data interoperability, the publicly available clear guidance and the tools to check data quality compliance (European Commission, 2025).

Energy modelling. Electricity has an important role across standards. Nevertheless, there are other energy types considered such as heating, cooling and compressed air for (ISO 14067, ISO 14068, ISO 22526); or even biofuels (ISO 14068). In terms of electricity, it is common to find the use of a hierarchy. This term is used to define data source precedence in electricity modelling by giving higher priority to firsthand foreground data rather than proxies or background data that do not necessarily reflect with accuracy the type of electricity consumed.

Renewable sourcing disclosure and double counting avoidance has increased its relevance and requisites along the time (Future Market Insights, 2025). This could explain why it should be considered in GHG Protocol and PAS 2050:2011; is explicitly mentioned in PEF; and includes hierarchy criteria in ISO 14068.

Generic data use (scope) can be used in EN 15804 and ISO 21930. The difference is that for EN15804 this can happen for the processes that the producer has no influence. Upstream losses in transport, distribution and downstream emissions are accounted in ISO 14067 reliant standards (ISO 14068 and ISO 22526).

Assumptions about electricity production shall be stated in ISO 21930.

Considering the above, clear hierarchy criteria (prioritizing primary data, supplier's mix for processes under manufacturer's control) and renewable sourcing disclosure is essential to avoid double counting or masked lowered impacts. This should apply for electricity, heating, cooling, and other energy vectors such as hydrogen (Green Hydrogen Organisation, 2023) which is not mentioned in the analyzed standards.

Moreover, we encourage cradle to grave system boundaries, assign the corresponding carbon footprint of the energy production, whether renewable or not, and allow, for the cut-off criteria, energy recovery without minimum requirements.

Emissions and removals with emphasis on biogenic carbon.

All standards share allocation criteria based on the inherent property of biogenic carbon, specifically the product's mass.

Two main approaches exist for accounting biogenic carbon flows in emissions and removals: (-1/+1), which considers these flows, and (0/0), which omits them. Given the scientific literature review and the legislative mapping, where removals are gaining momentum, this flow cannot be disregarded. Nevertheless, the interconnections between biogenic carbon, direct land use change, system boundaries and allocation criteria are crucial but often not consistently aligned between standards.

For example, while EN 16485 allows both biogenic carbon approaches, direct land use change modelling is not clear. It refers to significance criteria that point to EN 15804 that forwards to ISO 14067. The latter specifies that ISO 14067 cut-off criteria shall be used to know the significance (significant emissions) in EN 16485. Thus, it is not mandatory while there is evidence of the common bigger impact of direct land use change compared to biogenic carbon (Brandão, Heijungs, & Cowie, 2022).

This work advocates for a harmonization that allows whether 0/0 and/or -1/+1 approach only if dLUC is accounted with an internationally recognized methodology such as IPCC Guidelines (GHG Protocol, ISO 14067 or EF).

For this LCA structure we suggest -1/+1 approach only if cradle to grave study is performed. Otherwise, 0/0 is to be used. This allows more complete information about, for instance, emissions during the end of life, while keeping track of the credits associated with carbon removals. Precise instructions about the most adequate criteria to allocate credits along the supply chain is subject to further research and is being covered in scientific literature such as (Obrecht et al., 2021).

Carbon content. Its reporting is not mandatory in almost half of the analyzed standards (EN 15804 (for less than 5% mass in product), ISO 14067, ISO 14068, ISO 21930). Given that its reporting follows an informative purpose (i.e., for intermediate products in PEF) we advocate for disclosing this LCA structure as optional additional information for all scopes in LCA studies using a harmonized carbon content calculation such as the one included in ISO 22526

Carbon storage modelling follows different criteria. I.e., from exceeding 100 years and excepting carbon stock in managed forest (PAS 2050) to not being considered in PEF. Specific guidance is provided in some standards (ie., EN 15804). Since we support carbon neutrality principle for biogenic carbon (uptake balanced by end-of-life release modelling), a voluntary indicator for 'Temporary Carbon Storage' should be reported in units of 'kg CO₂eq/year.' This provides information for assessing a product's role in the circular bioeconomy without compromising the integrity of the GWP metric (Zieger et al., 2025).

Direct land use change. While dLUC reporting is mandatory across all screened standards, methodologies show great variability. Divergences exist in scope (e.g., exclusion of native forest removals in PEF and EN 15804), time horizons, the reference land baseline or temporal aspects such as inventory period or amortization period. Moreover metrics themselves can be different:

- Land use change metrics (sLUC and dLUC)
- Land tracking metrics (indirect land use change emissions, carbon opportunity cost, and land occupation).

Guidance often points to external sources like IPCC Guidelines or PAS 2050, yet implementation differs, highlighting a lack of internal consistency between methodological choices, such as the time horizon, reference land baseline or amortization (equal or linear) that can lead to very different results (Maciel et al., 2022).

We propose land use types definition alignment as well as methodological aspects such as the inventory, and the annualization period. For example, the latter does not have to be fixed on a 20-year period. They could comprehend other time frames such as 35 years to account for the period with highest deforestation of the last three decades (FAO, 2020). This opens the door to further research to estimate the most adequate parameters depending on the goal and scope of the study or decision for policy making.

We consider dLUC reporting essential, and its contribution to the total carbon footprint is sometimes higher than fossil or biogenic for certain products (i.e., nickel laterite extraction (Mervine et al., 2025)). Furthermore, given the variety of definitions for land use types, temporal aspects such as the inventory period, we recommend the land use types of IPCC classification. Moreover, if data is available, adding to Tier 1 accounting, Tier 2 is encouraged to improve reporting accuracy (IIED, 2023).

Indirect land use change (iLUC) is only available for reporting in P-CFP ISO 22526 and GHG Protocol Land Sector and Removals. One of the biggest differences stems from the modelling approach: Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) - general equilibrium (CGE) or the Global Biosphere Management Model among others. This creates substantial uncertainty (Ruth Delzeit, 2017). Therefore, if provided, we encourage the voluntary disclosure of iLUC as additional information clearly stating the model used.

Land management practices are considered in all analysed standards but in PAS 2050. The diversity in the focus normally corresponds to the coverage of the standard (from granular differentiation by fertilizer in PEF to specific forest management in EN 16485). We propose the accounting of land management practices as part of the dLUC subimpact category following a traceable method that considers permanence criteria. If no specific data is available, IPCC Guidelines factors can be used.

End of life considerations are included if they fall within the scope of ISO 14067 and PAS 2050:2011. So, if EoL is accounted, fossil and biogenic emissions from landfilling in PEF and several EN and ISO standards are to be considered as well.

PEF uses the CFF to model the life cycle stage where an activity occurs. Standards like EN 15804, EN 16485, and ISO 14067 guide environmental assessments for each module. Allocation methods for recycled materials, as per ISO 14067, ISO 14068, and ISO 22526, include open-loop (material recycled into different product systems with altered properties) and closed-loop (for closed-loop systems or open-loop systems where recycled material properties remain unchanged). PEF models reuse and refurbish as product lifetime extensions if specifications remain the same. While PEF has no minimum energy recovery requirements, EN 15804, EN 16485, and ISO 21930 require a minimum 60% energy efficiency for recovery. In GHG Protocol all emissions and removals from the system, including waste, should be allocated among the system's other outputs. If waste becomes useful and marketable in another system, it is no longer considered waste, but other types of outputs. Economic allocation is expected to yield more representative estimates.

Open-loop systems imply shared burdens and credits between product systems. The equations that indicate the share to each system should consider the average number of times a product is recycled and the quality of the final product while avoiding potential consequential LCA interpretations (Schrijvers et al., 2021). Allocation criteria (mass, energy, economic): depends on the purpose of the study, normally, mass or economic allocation should be selected depending on the goal and scope of the study and clearly justifying the selected criteria (Dominguez Aldama et al., 2023).

For congruence purposes with the quantitative cut-off criteria, no minimum energy recovery should be needed. This implies broader implementation and clarity for both the LCA modelling and the ESG reporting. EoL modelling should be mandatory and specific equations provided for adequate modelling such as in EF or EN 15804. Specific modelling criteria for burdens and credits allocation remain unclear and are currently addressed from both the scientific and policy dimension (European Commission, 2025).

Offsetting is reported in ISO 14068 only if needed to achieve carbon neutrality. Before, the entity shall reduce and implement GHG removals + additional requisites. Nevertheless, ISO 14068 does not specify how many emissions per type of sector or activity should be reduced before moving to GHG removals and additional requisites to, ultimately, apply offsetting. Loads and benefits can be reported separately. Offsetting in PEF shall be reported separately as additional environmental information. In EN 15804 carbon offset shall not be included in the

calculation of the GWP neither in ISO 14607 nor PAS 2050:2011. According to GHG Protocol offsetting can be reported, but separately from the scopes as well as loads and benefits.

This work suggests including offsetting as additional information since this activity operates beyond the system boundaries of attributional LCA (Brander, 2024). Moreover, emissions per type of sector or activity to be reduced should be specified before allowing offsetting.

Table 4. Results for each standard and LCA structures included in the impact assessment.

LCA struc.	EF Recommendation 2021/2279	EN 15804 2012 + A2 2019	EN 16760:2015	EN 16485 :2014	ISO 14067:2018
Climate change LCIA methods and timing	Literal Shall Shall GWP 100 AR5; uptake and emissions from different fossil and biogenic sources to be reported separately. Literal delayed emissions not considered.	Literal Shall GWP 100 IPCC; Literal Should supplementary requirements for including significant emissions beyond 100 years if expected.	Literal Shall GWP 100. Carbon feedbacks to be accounted. Literal Should other time horizons and metrics like GTP	Literal Shall Shall GWP 100 most recent AR. Information on the timing of removals and subsequent emissions is important	Literal Shall GWP 100 latest IPCC available. No delayed emissions. Literal Should Other GPW or GTP as additional information. Literal Shall Fossil and biogenic emissions and removals reported together but dLUc and aircraft emissions separately. Literal Should Timing and delayed emissions if to be included, as additional information
Land use impact category	Literal Should land use impacts like soil fertility optional	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	Literal Should as part of the land tracking metric: land occupation (ha)	Not mentioned
LCA struc.	ISO 21930:2017	PAS 2050, 2011	ISO 22526-2:2020	GHG Protocol Draft Land use sector and removals	ISO 14068:2023
Climate change LCIA methods and timing	Literal Shall GWP100 AR5. Delayed emissions if to be reported, as additional information not LCA related.	Literal Shall GWP100 IPCC 2013 - fixed with 4 categories (same as EF). Temporary nor delayed emissions to be accounted in GWP.	Literal Shall GWP100 for temporal accounting. Interpreted May For emissions and removals in general unclear guidance to EN 16214. For LULUC GHG accounting IPCC guidelines or RED guidelines could be used.	As EN 15804	Literal Shall GWP 100 latest IPCC available. No delayed emissions. Literal Should Other GPW or GTP as additional information. Literal Shall Fossil and biogenic emissions and removals reported together but dLUc and aircraft emissions separately.
Land use impact category	Literal Shall soil quality index for land occupation and transformation - LANCA model	Literal Should Additional environmental information - Potential Soil quality Index based on LANCA	Literal Should To be documented: initial and resulting land use/cover; agriculture production time. Any land use method to be used with a	As EN 15804	Not mentioned

			careful review. I.e.: PDF, BDP, SOM or ecosystem services		
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LCIA method in climate change. There is a split between using the "latest available" IPCC Global Warming Potential (GWP) values (as in ISO 14067) and a fixed version like "IPCC 2013" (as in EN 15804 for construction products). The former prioritizes scientific accuracy at a given moment, while the latter prioritizes comparability over time, a crucial feature for EPDs where benchmarks must remain stable (Moré et al., 2022).

Subimpact categories are used in most of the standards, but they vary (CC-total + fossil + biogenic + dluc in PEF) to Fossil + biogenic + dLUC + aircraft (ISO 14067) or categories and subcategories in the GHG Protocol. Since these standards originate from different mandates they have different accounting metrics.

Furthermore, the treatment of emission timing exposes a critical flaw in conventional LCA. The widespread reliance on a static 100-year snapshot, as highlighted by ISO 14067's frank admission of its arbitrary nature "there is no scientific basis for choosing a 100-year time horizon compared to other time horizons", is a significant oversimplification. This is a form of temporal burden shifting that masks the true climate impact profile of products, particularly those in the circular or bioeconomy. This work proposes, based on ILCD compliant datasets and congruence with previous recommendations, harmonization to CC-total + fossil + biogenic + dLUC subimpact categories and the latest available GWP values as the most common metric although not being the most accurate (Brandão et al., 2024).

Only ISO 21930 considers delayed emissions, and as additional non-mandatory information. On the one hand, in PEF and ISO 14067, delayed emissions are not considered.

Land use (LU) impact category presents also a variety of modelling options according to each standard. The soil quality index with LANCA method in EF, EN 15804 (and EN 16485 as additional indicator). In the GHG Protocol land occupation (ha) is used as one of the land tracking metrics. Other metrics are also used such as PDF or Biodiversity Damage Potential (EN 16760). Nevertheless, the other analyzed standards do not report this impact category since it is outside their carbon footprint scope.

This impact category goes beyond carbon modelling, although useful to consider trade-offs and opportunities, especially for case studies (Hammar et al., 2024). Therefore, we suggest its reporting as voluntary additional information.

Finally, it must be noted that **single score** is only considered in PEF.

Some more general proposals to move towards harmonization are:

- A critical step is developing a common glossary of key carbon modelling terms (e.g., 'biogenic carbon,' 'dLUC,' 'environmental significance for cut-off'), potentially through a

CEN/ISO joint working group, building on IPCC guidelines but resolving existing ambiguities highlighted in our analysis (see SEM for definition comparisons).

- Further research is needed to quantify the magnitude of difference in carbon footprint results when applying different standard's rules (e.g., for dLUC or EoL) to common product systems.
- Consider modelling in other methodologies comprehensively. I.e., ISO 14068 mapping with GHG Protocol but for a broader number of standards.
- Enforcing a rigorous scientific approach to prevent modelling trade-offs, especially in allocation and biogenic carbon accounting.
- Ensuring all methodological assumptions and their scientific basis are transparently reported and verifiable.

In general, carbon modelling standards harmonization could be structured as shown in Table 5, where each driver has one or several required actions and some examples for implementation are provided.

Table 5. Harmonization drivers, required actions and examples for carbon modelling standards.

Harmonization drivers	Required actions	Examples
Definitions	Identify inconsistencies.	Some dLUC data can be available in CORINE land cover nomenclature but not in IPCC land use types for GHG national inventories (Intergovernmental Panel On Climate Change, 2022), especially for Tier 2 and 3. CORINE nomenclature includes land use-focused (LU) classes (especially within the artificial surfaces group) and some classes having mixed LC / LU character (European Environment Agency, 2021). We encourage the development of a methodology or tool to map land cover/use nomenclatures oriented to IPCC classification while allowing carbon stock monitoring (i.e., for CRCF reporting and decision making (European Commission, 2024).
	Agree on nomenclature (see SEM 1): +Already in use +Aligned with IPCC as long as possible	
Models	Inventory of methods for each LCA structure	I.e., for biogenic carbon modelling approaches or dLUC (qualitative analysis) (European Commission, 2025).
	Assess their readiness for multisectorial use	
	Asses their similarity to map them	
Quantify differences between standards	Identify where the biggest deviations occur and why	dLUC deviations due to modelling and temporal aspect assumptions (Maciel et al., 2022). EoL deviations from different allocation criteria for burden and credit allocation as well as system boundaries (Obrecht et al., 2021).

	Use best available knowledge to focus quantification and mapping efforts on the most significant LCA structures according to their carbon footprint while testing other impact categories for which scientific evidence claim significant impact.	Water use for lignin-based polyols can be higher than the petroleum-based equivalent (Staccioli et al., 2024), despite aiming at a generally lower environmental impact, due to chemicals consumption (i.e., H ₂ SO ₄).
Mapping standards	Start with the most similar standards considering scope, definitions and models alignment for each LCA structure. I.e., PEF and EN 15804 life cycle stages, modules, EoL equations, etc.	Map EoL equations: CFF (PEF) and Annex 4 (EN 15804) based on current EU policies and industry needs. Generic EoL modelling is not adequate. Ongoing efforts to meet precise sectorial modelling needs (European Commission, 2025).
	Agree on a set of common modelling criteria (scope, definitions, metrics, etc.) for related standards. +Consensual and transversal definitions + Agree on a method for each LCA structure avoiding divergence between them.	Similar to the mapping (ISO, 2023) with GHG Protocol but comprehending several standards, starting with the most similar ones to then tackle the more divergent or specific for given LCA structures.

Additionally, lately there is a fast development and update of standards on carbon modelling. Some examples include EN 18027 Bio-based products - Life cycle assessment (DIN, 2023) which has just been published. This standard follows the requirements of ISO 14067 and EN 16760. I.e., LCA structures like biogenic carbon (modelling approach -1/+1 or 0/0 only when biogenic carbon is completely oxidized), dLUC follows IPCC methods, carbon storage as additional information and covers impact categories like land use, biodiversity or microplastics (providing detailed guidance).

4. CONCLUSIONS

A grey literature review was carried out including European legislation and focusing on some of the most relevant sectors in carbon modelling: biobased products, plastics and construction. This work presents a novel LCA framework for the comprehensive analysis of carbon modelling related standards that deepens from LCA structures into LCA elements.

By acknowledging the unclear picture for decision making or ecodesign of present carbon modelling in standards, this analysis allows to identify some of the gaps and challenges. It also provides suggestions to link standards to, for instance, identify emission transfer between LCA structures (i.e., from biogenic carbon to dLUC depending on the selected biogenic carbon approach). Also to identify trade-offs between impact categories (from climate change to water use) while aiming at becoming a practical tool for policy alignment regarding ESG reporting. We suggest aligning definitions and models, quantify differences between standards for given LCA structures and mapping between standards as well as particular guidance for each LCA structure.

Some of the implications of this work could include more uniform LCA studies at product level (definitions, benchmarking, etc.) or enhanced comparability, as well as easiness to draft ESG reports. Nonetheless, this would require substantial effort from standards boards, policy makers, industry and academia.

In all, this work provides, under the prism of a legislative mapping, scientific and standards analysis, a comprehensive LCA methodology and analysis to support standards comparison. The aim is to provide an actionable tool for LCA practitioners and policy making to contribute to carbon modelling standards harmonization. This is, to prevent trade-offs, simplify environmental reporting and enhance comparability between LCA studies as well as ESG report transparency.

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REFERENCES

- Andreasi Bassi, S. B. (2023). *Updated characterisation and normalisation factors for the Environmental Footprint 3.1 method*. Joint Research Center; European Commission.
- Andreasi Bassi, S. G. (2024). *Draft Quantifying the climate change impacts of the biogenic carbon flows under the EC's products Environmental Footprint method*. JRC EU Commission.
- Brandão, M., Heijungs, R., & Cowie, A. L. (2022). On quantifying sources of uncertainty in the carbon footprint of biofuels: crop/feedstock, LCA modelling approach, land-use change, and GHG metrics. *Biofuel Research Journal*.
- BSI. (2011). *PAS 2050, 2011 Specification for the assessment of the life cycle GHG emissions of goods and services* .
- CEN. (2011). *FprCEN/TR 16214-5:2011 (E) Sustainability criteria for the production of biofuels and bioliquids for energy applications - Principles, criteria, indicators and verifiers - Part 5: Guidance towards definition of residue and waste via a positive list*.
- CEN. (2013). *EN 16214-4:2013+A1 Sustainability criteria for the production of biofuels and bioliquids for energy applications - Principles, criteria, indicators and verifiers - Part 4: Calculation methods of the greenhouse gas emission balance using a life cycle analy*.
- CEN. (2014). *EN 16485:2014 EPD - Round and sawn timber – Product category rules for wood and wood-based products for use in construction*.
- CEN. (2015). *EN 16760:2015 Bio-based products – Life Cycle Assessment*.
- CEN. (2018). *FprCEN/TS 16214-2:2018 (E) Sustainability criteria for the production of biofuels and bioliquids for energy applications - Principles, criteria, indicators and verifiers - Part 2: Conformity assessment including chain of custody and mass balance*.

- CEN. (2019). *EN 15804:2012+A2:2019 EPD - Sustainability of construction works – Core rules for the product category of construction products.*
- CEN. (2021). *CWA 17675:2021 (CEN WORKSHOP AGREEMENT) Mapping of the mandatory and voluntary carbon management framework in the EU.*
- CEN. (2022). *CWA 17898 (CEN WORKSHOP AGREEMENT) Methodology to quantify the global agricultural crop footprint including soil impacts.*
- CEN. (2022). *prEN 16214-3:2022 (E) Sustainability and greenhouse gas emission saving criteria for biomass for energy applications - Principles, criteria, indicators and verifiers - Part 3: Sustainability criteria related to environmental aspects.*
- CEN. (2023). *FprEN 16214-1:2023 (E) Sustainability and greenhouse gas emission saving criteria for biomass for energy applications - Principles, criteria, indicators and verifiers - Part 1: Terminology.*
- Cerulogy & Fraunhofer. (2023). *Support to the development of methodologies for the certification of industrial carbon removals with permanent storage.*
- CRETA. (2023). *Review of certification methodologies for carbon farming . Wageningen University and Research.*
- CRETA. (2023). *Review of certification methodologies for long-term biogenic carbon storage in buildings.*
- DIN. (2023). *Bio-based products - Life cycle assessment - Additional requirements and guidelines for comparing the life cycles of bio-based products with their fossil-based equivalents; German and English version prEN 18027:2023.*
- Elfriede Penz, P. P. (2018). How do companies reduce their carbon footprint and how do they communicate these measures to stakeholders? *Journal of Cleaner Production.*

Endrit Hoxha, A. P. (2020). Biogenic carbon in buildings: a critical overview of LCA methods. *Building and cities*.

European Commission. (2018). Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2018/2066 of 19 December 2018 on the monitoring and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions pursuant to Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and amending Commission Regulation (EU) No 601. *EUR-Lex*.

European Commission. (2021). *Commission Recommendation (EU) 2021/2279 of 15 December 2021 on the use of the Environmental Footprint methods to measure and communicate the life cycle environmental performance of products and organisations*.

European Commission. (2023). *Directive (EU) 2023/2413 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 October 2023 amending Directive (EU) 2018/2001, Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 and Directive 98/70/EC as regards the promotion of energy from renewable sources, and repealing Council .*

European Commission. (2023). *Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law)*.

European Commission. (2023). *Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 May 2023 on the making available on the Union market and the export from the Union of certain commodities and products associated with deforestation and forest degradation and r.*

European Commission. (2023). *Regulation (EU) 2023/2405 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 October 2023 on ensuring a level playing field for sustainable air transport (ReFuelEU Aviation)*.

European Commission. (2024). Regulation 2024 laying down harmonised conditions for the marketing of construction products .

European Commission. (2024). *egulation (EU) 2024/1735 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 on establishing a framework of measures for strengthening Europe’s net-zero technology manufacturing ecosystem and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724.*

European Commission. (2024). *European Commission Expert Group Register*. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/core/api/front/document/108204/download>

European Commission. (2024). *Regulation (EU) 2024/1781 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 establishing a framework for the setting of ecodesign requirements for sustainable products, amending Directive (EU) 2020/1828 and Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 and repeal.*

European Commission. (2024). *Regulation (EU) 2024/1991 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 June 2024 on nature restoration and amending Regulation (EU) 2022/869.*

European Commission. (2024). *REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL establishing a Union certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products .*

European Commission. (2025, November 11). Retrieved from CBAM: Call for evidence on emission methodology, free allocation adjustment and carbon price paid in third countries: <https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/news/cbam-call-evidence-emission-methodology-free-allocation-adjustment-and-carbon-price-paid-third-2025-08->

- European Platform on LCA. (2024). *Global Guidance on Environmental Life Cycle Impact Assessment Indicators (GLAM)*. Retrieved from <https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/glam.html>
- FAO. (2020). *Global Forest Resources Assessment 2020 Key findings*. Rome.
- FAO. (2022). *FAO strategy on Climate Change 2022-2031*. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Fortune Business Insights. (2024, 11 11). Retrieved from <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/carbon-accounting-software-market-107292>
- Future Market Insights. (2025). *Renewable Energy Certificate Market Size and Share Forecast Outlook 2025 to 2035*.
- Green Hydrogen Organisation. (2023). *Green Hydrogen Standard 2.0*.
- Haoran Lei, W. Y.-Q. (2025). Anatomy of methods for measuring life cycle carbon emission of built environment. *Journal of Building Engineering*.
- IIED. (2023). *Promoting accuracy in GHG inventories through use of higher-tier methods: a practical guide for LDCs and other developing countries*.
- ISO. (2006). *ISO 14044:2006 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines*.
- ISO. (2006). *ISO 14064-3:2006 GHG Specification with guidance for the validation and verification of GHG assertions*.
- ISO. (2014). *ISO 14046:2014 Environmental management — Water footprint*.
- ISO. (2014). *ISO 14072:2014 LCA on organizational level*.
- ISO. (2017). *ISO 21930:2017 Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works. Core rules for EPD of construction products and services*.
- ISO. (2018). *ISO 14067:2018 GHG — Carbon footprint of products*.

- ISO. (2019). *ISO 14064-2:2019 GHG Specification with guidance at the project level for quantification, monitoring and reporting of GHG emission reductions or removal enhancements.*
- ISO. (2020). *ISO 22526_1:2020 Carbon and environmental footprint of biobased plastics - General principles .*
- ISO. (2020). *ISO 22526_2:2020 Carbon and environmental footprint of biobased plastics - Material carbon footprint, amount (mass) of CO₂ removed from the air and incorporated into polymer molecule.*
- ISO. (2020). *ISO 22526_3:2020 Carbon and environmental footprint of biobased plastics - Process carbon footprint, requirements and guidelines for quantification.*
- ISO. (2020). *ISO 22526_4:2020 Carbon and environmental footprint of biobased plastics - Environmental (total) footprint (Life Cycle Assessment).*
- ISO. (2021). *ISO 14021:2016/Amd.2021 Environmental labels and declarations — Self-declared environmental claims (Type II environmental labelling) AMENDMENT 1: Carbon footprint, carbon neutral.*
- ISO. (2022). *ISO 14074:2022 Environmental Management – Life cycle assessment - Principles, requirements and guidelines for normalization, weighting and interpretation.*
- ISO. (2023). *ISO 14068-1:2023 Climate change management — Transition to net zero Part 1: Carbon neutrality.*
- Jinying Xu, K. M. (2024). Carbon data and its requirements in infrastructure-related GHG standards. *Environmental Science and Policy.*
- Joint Research Center, European Commission. (2023). *European Platform on Life Cycle Assessment.* Retrieved from <https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/LCDN/EN15804.xhtml>

- JRC, European Commission. (2010). *ILCD Handbook* .
- Lena Klaaßen, C. S. (2021). Harmonizing corporate carbon footprints. *Nature Communications*.
- OCDE. (2023). *What Future for Climate and Trade? Scenarios and Strategies for Carbon Competitiveness*. OCDE.
- Oliver J. Robinson, A. T. (2017). Towards a universal carbon footprint standard: A case study of carbon management at universities. *Journal of Cleaner Production*.
- Reuters. (2024, 11 26). *Reuters*. Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com/markets/commodities/cop29-countries-endorse-global-carbon-market-framework-2024-11-11/>
- Ruth Delzeit, G. K. (2017). *Indirect land use change (iLUC) revisited: an evaluation of key policy proposals*.
- Sven van Baren, E. A. (2023). *Review of certification methodologies for carbon farming – survey results and first assessment of coverage of the Q.U.A.L.I.T.Y criteria*.
- Tao Gao, Q. L. (2013). A comparative study of carbon footprint and assessment standards. *International Journal of Low-Carbon Technologies*.
- Theresa Pscherer, S. K. (2024). LCA standards for environmental product assessments in the bioeconomy with a focus on biogenic carbon: A systematic review. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*.
- UNEP. (2020). *Roadmap for national LCA database development*.
- V. Tascione, C. A.-D. (2024). A comparative analysis of recent life cycle assessment guidelines and frameworks for the plastic packaging industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*.
- World Resources Institute & WBCSD. (2015). *GHG protocol: Corporate Value Chain (Scope 3) Standard*.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Supporting Information S1 includes:

Table S1-A: Complete list of screened standards.

Table S1-B: Summary of the EU carbon modelling legislative mapping and their linkage to standards and interpretation.

Table S1-C: Key features from EU certification framework technical reports and their linkage to standards and interpretation.

Supporting Information S2 includes:

Excel file detailing general and summary comparative analysis of the ten standards, taking into account the defined LCA structures and elements.

Figure Legends

Figure 1. Summary of the methodology followed for literature and standards screening and comparison.....	4
Figure 2. Selection of scientific literature focused on carbon modelling with an LCA approach.	5
Figure 3. LCA structures from ISO 14040 framework.....	9